

PROFESSIONAL INFLUENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS

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Abstract. *In the educational process, the teacher's professional skills, practical and methodical experiences are related to the high level of use of their individual characteristics and the formation of the ability to work individually. In this case, it is important to have pedagogical efficiency, the sum of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and the culture of pedagogical behavior.*

Keywords: *professional skills, pedagogical efficiency, creativity, competence, research, ability.*

The success of reforms implemented in the education system directly depends on the professional skills and literacy of the teacher. The training of the holders of these professions to the extent that they are well-educated and responsible for the education of young people has always been an urgent problem. After all, it is the responsibility of the teacher to inculcate national values and national thinking in the minds of young people in a stronger and more perfect way.

It is known that, as in all fields, professional skills are formed and improved in a teacher over the years both practically and theoretically. It is worth noting that the basic ground for a teacher's professional skills, practical and methodological experiences is created in a higher education institution. Because the teacher's professional skill is a very complex and national process, its acquisition, as noted above, is formed by the teacher's many years of effective research and creative work. However, since the scientific and practical basis of the secrets of skill is not formed in time for the student in higher educational institutions, its discovery in the process of work after the higher educational institution does not always appear by itself.

Educators of citizens who have matured in all respects, adapted to the advanced lifestyle in society, are always aware of educational and vocational programs and the latest achievements of pedagogical technologies, who have conscious social-political, legal, psychological-pedagogical knowledge, who feel responsible before the state and family. The teacher should have high theoretical and methodological training. A new approach, a new methodology, and a new professional skill are required for a teacher who is in line with the requirements of the present time, who has mastered the latest achievements of science and technology, and who can apply our national and spiritual values to the educational system.

Being a skilled master of his profession, a teacher first of all depends on how he uses his individual characteristics at a high level and how the ability to work individually is formed. This method is formed in the process of training and practical training at a higher educational institution and consists of a system of individual, unique methods that ensure success in the future. The idea of forming professional skills and effectiveness of future teachers should be in the leading position in the training of specialists in higher education institutions. There can be different ways to develop highly qualified professional skills. The future teacher has professional knowledge, skills and having a set of skills, a culture of pedagogical behavior is the main foundation of professional-pedagogical efficiency.

There are three directions for the formation of highly skilled effective teachers in higher pedagogical educational institutions carried out according to:

- thorough training in one's specialty (professional and pedagogical - psychological knowledge);
- the culture of acquiring methodological knowledge;
- pedagogical creativity and creativity.

The system of professional education in higher pedagogic educational institutions forms a future specialist and prepares him for future professional activity. A complex set of professional qualities that a modern specialist should have can be acquired by students in the process of traditional training and practice. In the process of professional training all Positive features can be formed when the shortcomings of the current education system are eliminated and they are supplemented with new modern knowledge.

One of the important aspects of career orientation of students is its pedagogical culture, which is implemented in various directions of the system of psychological and pedagogical sciences. For example: methodologically V.A. Slastenin, G.V. Bragina, ethically - aesthetically I.P. Rachenko, D.S. Yakovleva, communicative aspects A.V. Mudrik, O.O. Kiseleva, V.P. Simonov, technological aspects were developed by M.M. Levina, N.E. Shurkova.

In particular, the teacher's technological culture is an important creative skill that reveals individual pedagogical activity as an important aspect of professional skills in the course of his technological activity. Technological training of the teacher is an important part of understanding the category of "pedagogical effectiveness" and it reflects the essence of pedagogical culture, which performs the tasks of perception and preservation of pedagogical reality. Today, the technological culture of the teacher, which is considered as the basis of success in the professional activity of the future teacher, consists of a process that directs the inner potential of students to the creative direction.

Every student should have fundamental knowledge, professional qualifications and skills, regardless of the specialty and nature of future professional activity. Creativity, research and experience of independent activity, which allows the future specialist to clarify his point of view on this or that question or problem related to his profession, are important in acquiring this knowledge, skills and abilities.

The constituent features of each of the following three blocks (basic, methodological, creative) are important in the development of the future teacher's professional skills:

Base factor knowledge of basic sciences; teaching methodology; philosophical knowledge; pedagogical knowledge; psychological knowledge; includes features of professional-pedagogical training such as pedagogical ethics.

To methodological efficiency knowledge of methodological knowledge corresponding to the level of philosophical, general and specific sciences, educational problems, integral, activity-related knowledge based on an independent approach is embodied.

The effectiveness of creative pedagogical skills orientation to professional values; focus on motivational creativity; understanding the main problems of innovation in education; focusing on a systematic approach to solving pedagogical tasks; programmatic - target planning ability; scientific - research, technological and graphic culture; professional ethics; ability to independently understand educational problems; communicativeness; cordiality; professional flexibility; be prepared for unexpected situations; permeability methods and methodologies; the

ability to overcome various prejudices that cause negative situations; ergonomic thinking; individual style of professional activity; ability to assess one's professional qualities, reflexive assessment of one's activity and its results, criticism and self-criticism; characteristics such as self-development and the ability to learn independently are embodied.

Professional pedagogical education can have a negative impact on the effectiveness of the educational process as a result of the student's inability to get enough direction in the changing curriculum with the demands of the modern educational environment.

The requirements for the high level of training and moral level of the learner are also updated. A creative teacher should be able to distinguish the new pedagogical technology methodology in his field and be able to effectively apply it in practice.

It is not for nothing that special importance is attached to "pedagogical technique" in "Pedagogical technology" nowadays. After all, the pedagogical technique embodies the professional talent that represents the activity arising from the internal capabilities of the teacher. This is especially evident when determining the level of professional maturity of teachers. To be able to perceive the appearance and clothing of the teacher correctly, to be able to convey the place of some words to the student's mind with "mimic" and "pantomime" gestures, to be able to control one's emotions and mood, to express words based on the subject of the lesson in a correct and literary language, qualities such as clarity in pronunciation, fluency of speech are formed based on the possibilities of "pedagogical technique". The scientific, literary and methodical aspects that represent the characteristics of the teacher's language should not be ignored.

The highest step in mastering the secrets of skill of the future teacher is determined by his pedagogical professional efficiency. A skilled student always learns best practices quickly. Therefore, in pedagogy, concepts such as "new", "advanced", "innovation", "creativity", "professional thinking" are integrated into the concept of "professional agency". The development of these concepts is reflected in pedagogical skills.

In conclusion, the research of the professional factor of the teacher in mastering the secrets of pedagogical skills can be a separate topic. The main goals and tasks of improving professional efficiency are directed to the formation, generalization, and practical application of pedagogical skills in the future teacher.

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